

ANTIBACTERIAL INVESTIGATION OF TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES CONTAINING BENZALDEHYDE-DERIVED SCHIFF BASES: A REVIEW

Priyanka Swami*, Vibha Chaudhary, Aman Bishnoi, Mohammed Bilal, Narendar Bhojak, Raja Ram

GCRC, P. G. Department of Chemistry, Govt. Dungar College, (NAAC 'A' Grade) MGS University, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India 334001.

Article Received on 13 May 2026,
Article Revised on 03 June 2026,
Article Published on 10 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20627168>

*Corresponding Author

Priyanka Swami

GCRC, P. G. Department of
Chemistry, Govt. Dungar College,
(NAAC 'A' Grade) MGS University,
Bikaner, Rajasthan, India 334001.

How To Cite This Article: Priyanka Swami*, Vibha Chaudhary, Aman Bishnoi, Mohammed Bilal, Narendar Bhojak, Raja Ram (2026). Antibacterial Investigation Of Transition Metal Complexes Containing Benzaldehyde-Derived Schiff Bases : A Review. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 1732-1759.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Schiff bases are fascinating compounds formed when carbonyl and amino compounds undergo condensation. These versatile molecules have found their applications into numerous industries and are recognized for their impressive range of biological activities. The synthesis of new Schiff base-derived compounds remains of interest due to increasing problem of antibiotic resistance in clinical practice. In recent years, application of Schiff bases derived from benzaldehyde have become very fascinating to researchers as it have a great potential as Antibacterial, Antimalarial, Ant cancerous, Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory agent. Complexing with transition metals increases the biological effectiveness of the Schiff ligands. This review brings key studies from past few years, highlighting the antibacterial properties of Schiff base derived from benzaldehyde and their transition metal complexes.

KEYWORDS: *Transition metal complex, Schiff base, Antibacterial activity, Benzaldehyde.*

INTRODUCTION

New drugs development is crucial for human health because people are facing many health related problems. Bacterial contaminations arise when infective microorganisms enter the

body and selectively target specific organs, leading to distinct clinical conditions depending on the site of infection. Pneumonia is caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Additionally, *Salmonella typhi* produces typhoid fever by affecting both the intestinal tract and bloodstream. *Escherichia coli* is frequently linked to food poisoning in the digestive tract. *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are commonly responsible for skin infections such cellulitis and boils. *Escherichia coli* is still the most common infection in the urinary tract, although bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* can cause osteomyelitis in the bones and joints.^[1-4]

In summary, bacteria can affect almost every organ system, therefore effective treatment necessitates a variety of strategies, such as antibiotic treatment (including Penicillin, Amoxicillin, and Tetracycline), combination therapy, surgical procedures, supportive care, vaccination, probiotic treatment, metallodrugs (metal-containing antimicrobial agents), and innovative methods like phage therapy. The extensive overprescription and improper use of antibiotics have hastened the development of antimicrobial resistance, greatly diminishing the effectiveness of standard treatments. Thus, there is an immediate need for innovative therapies that can address current challenges and provide safer, more targeted, and effective solutions to ultimately enhance the overall clinical experience for patients.^[5-6] The accomplishment in these fields can be enhanced through the creation of different metallodrugs, as metal-based coordination compounds exhibit unique electronic characteristics, remarkable chemical reactivity, and redox activity.^[7-12] Benzaldehyde has been widely investigated for its antibacterial properties, but its limited effectiveness has encouraged the development of Schiff base derivatives, which exhibit improved biological activity, especially after complexation with transition metals.

Benzaldehyde is a manageable aromatic aldehyde, have noteworthy importance in pharmaceutical chemistry due to its structural versatility and high reactivity. Benzaldehyde is a key building block in the formation of numerous pharmaceutical constituents and it contributes to the development of Schiff bases, and other biologically active molecules.^[13-14] Benzaldehyde owns an extremely activated aldehyde group that readily involves in the reactions with primary amines and forming Schiff bases which are key intermediates in medicinal chemistry. Due to its structural versatility and chemical reactivity, benzaldehyde works as a crucial source material for creating more complex molecular designs in drug development.^[15-17]

The coordination of benzaldehyde and its structural analogue with transition metal ions has unlocked a new paths in the progress of metallodrugs. When benzaldehyde creates complexes with transition metals frequently through altered derivatives like Schiff bases, it significantly improves the biological and chemical properties of the resultant compound.^[18] These metal-ligand complexes display enhanced stability, target-specific interactions, redox activity, and making them capable applicants in antibacterial treatment. In particular, metal-bound benzaldehyde derivatives have revealed the capacity to generate highly active oxygen species thereby increasing their therapeutic efficiency compared to their uncoordinated complements. The flexibility of benzaldehyde as a ligand is excellent thus it plays an important role in progressing metal-based drug design.^[19-21]

ANTIBACTERIAL STUDY

Ali Alshrefe et al. have prepared a new Schiff base ligand (E)-5-((2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylidene)amino)-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazole-3-one (L_1) (Figure No. 1 & Table No. 1). Metal complex $[M(L_1)_2(H_2O)_2]$ have prepared with Hg (II), Ni (II), Zn (II), Cu (II), Mn (II), Co (II), Cd (II), Pt (IV) metals. All compounds have tested for their antimicrobial activity against bacterial strains *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Results showed that the Hg(II) complex exhibited the highest inhibition activity against *S. aureus* (Table No. 2). Cu(II) complex and Hg(II) complex showed higher inhibition activity than free ligand.^[22] D. T. Sakhare have prepared a Schiff ligand (L_2) and its metal complex have prepared with Ni(II), and Co(II) metals. All compounds have tested for their antibacterial activity in opposed to *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*. Results revealed that complexes have higher activity than ligand alone.^[23] K. J. Thakkar et al. have prepared^[23] compound L_3 and its metal complexes have prepared using Ni, Fe, Cu, Cd, Mn, Cr, V, Co, Zn transition metal salts. Lemon juice have used as natural acid catalyst to make imine, and to enhance yield. All compounds have investigated for their antibacterial against bacterial strains (*S. aureus*, *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*). Results showed that both Schiff base and its metal complex have significant activity.^[24] K. M. Wahdan et al. have prepared compound L_4 and its metal complexes with Mn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Zr(IV) salts. All prepared compounds have tested for their antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*. Results showed that all compounds exhibited significant effectiveness to resist *B. subtilis*. Complex made with Zr metal have larger effect than the standard Gentamicin.^[25] I. Elaeraj et al. have prepared 4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)-N,N-dimethylaniline (L_5) and its mono and bimetallic complexes have made with Cu, Zn and Co metals. Compounds have tested for their activity

against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*. The $\text{Co}_2(\text{L}_5)_2(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ complex have highest antibacterial activity with 0.078 mg/mL, 0.009 mg/mL, and 0.039 mg/mL MIC value against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *E. coli* respectively. The $\text{Zn}(\text{L}_5)_2\text{Cl}_2$ complex showed moderate activity against *E. coli* with 0.625 mg/mL MIC value.^[26] Subin Kumar K. have synthesized a Schiff ligand (L_6) using ultrasonically assisted green chemical method. This ligand was later utilized as a capping agent for cadmium sulfide nanoparticles (CdS NPs), resulting in the formation of Schiff base-capped CdS nanoparticles (L-CdS NPs). Antibacterial activity of the prepared compounds have investigated against *S. aureus*, *B. cereus*, *S. cricetid*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* and findings revealed that Schiff base-capped CdS nanoparticles exhibited relatively low MIC values, suggesting their strong effectiveness as antibacterial agents.^[27] Laila H. Abdel-Rahman et al. have prepared compound L_7 and its metal complex using $[\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$, $[\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, and $[\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ metal salts. Compounds have tested for their inhibitory activity against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris*. All examined bacteria were effectively inhibited by the CuL_7 complex. The ZnL_7 complex was only effective against *B. subtilis* and *P. vulgaris*, whereas the NiL complex was highly effective against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, and *P. vulgaris*. There was little action of the VOL_7 complex against *B. subtilis*.^[28] Gehad Abd El-Hakeem et al. have prepared compound L_8 and its metal complexes have designed with $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ salts. All compounds have tested for their activity to inhibit *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. marcescens*, *B. cereus*, *M. luteus*, and *S. aureus* strains and the results revealed that pure ligand have zero potential to inhibit bacterial strains but its metal complexes have some activity and they follow the inhibition trend $\text{Zn complex} > \text{Ni complex} > \text{pure ligand}$.^[29]

Figure No. 1: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 1: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Sr. No.	Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
1	L ₁	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃	(E)-5-((2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino)-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazole-3-one"
2	L ₂	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ I ₂	2-[(3,5-diiodo-2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]-4-hydroxy-6-methyl pyrimidine
3	L ₃	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	(E)-2-(((4-chloro-2-nitrophenyl)imino)methyl)phenol
4	L ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	2-[(5-methyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)iminomethyl]benzene-1,3-diol
5	L ₅	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)-N,N-dimethylaniline
6	L ₆	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	N,N'-bis(benzylidene)-2-hydroxyacetophenone-1,2-ethylenediamine
7	L ₇	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	(E)-2-[(2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propanoyl)hydrazono]methyl-6-methoxy phenol
8	L ₈	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₅ O	(E)-2-[(2,4-diamino-6-phenyl-1,3,5-triazin-1-yl)imino]methyl-1-naphthol

Table No. 2: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	13.3mm	Ampicillin
	<i>E. coli</i>	-	15.7mm	
Hg-L ₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	27.6mm	
Cd-L ₁	<i>E. coli</i>	-	26.3mm	
L ₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	18.00mm	Penicillin
	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	22.38mm	
Co-L ₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	19.76mm	
Cr-L ₃	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	0.68mm	Tetracycline control
	<i>B. cereus</i>	-	0.65mm	
L ₄	<i>B. Subtilis</i>	-	35mm	Gentamicin
Zr-L ₄	<i>B. Subtilis</i>	-	41mm	
L ₅	<i>S. aureus</i>	5000µg/mL	-	-
Co ₂ (L ₅) ₂ (µ-Cl) ₂	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	9µg/mL	-	-
L ₆	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	1.1µg/mL	-	Cefpodoxime
L ₆ -CdS	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	0.14µg/mL	-	
L ₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	38.46 % a. i.	Gentamycin
Cu-L ₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	80.77 % a. i.	
L ₈	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	No activity	Chloramphenicol
Zn-L ₈	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	13 mm	

Activity index (%) or (a. i.) = $\frac{\text{Inhibition zone of compound (mm)}}{\text{Inhibition zone of standard drug (mm)}} \times 100$

M. A. Islam et al. have designed different transition metal complex with Isoniazid-based Schiff base ligand namely, N-benzylideneisonicotinohydrazide (L₉) (Figure No. 2 & Table No. 3) and with Cu(II), Ni(II), and Co(II) metal ions. Antibacterial activity test have performed for all the prepared compounds against two gram positive (*Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*), and two gram negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Shigella flexinerii*)

bacteria. Cu complex showed the maximum activity against gram positive bacteria (Table No. 4).^[30] L. d. O. Amaral et al. have designed two Palladium complex $[Pd(L_{10})(HL_{10})]Cl$ (1) and $[Pd(HL_{11})_2]$ (2) by the reaction of 4,5-Methylenedioxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L_{10}) and 5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde- β -alanine (L_{11}) with bis(acetonitrile)dichloro palladium(II). All the prepared compounds have checked for their antimicrobial action in opposed to *Streptococcus mutans* strain. Results discovered that Complexation with palladium(II) significantly improved the antimicrobial capability of the pure ligands.^[31] A. G. Ahmed and colleagues have prepared a new series of ligands 6,6¹-((2-phenylene-bis(azaneylylidene))bis(methaneylylidene))bis(2-ethoxyphenol)(L_{12}), 6,6¹-((pyridine-2,6-diylbis(azaneylylidene))bis(methaneylylidene))bis(2-ethoxyphenol) (L_{13}) and 4-((3-ethoxy-2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)pyrimidin-2(1H) one (L_{14}). Antimicrobial potential of all the prepared compounds have tested. Results showed that L_{14} ligand have good antibacterial activity in opposed to almost all tested bacterial strains.^[32] E. J. Waheed et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand (L_{15}) and its metal complex have prepared with VO(II), Cr(II), and Cu(II) metals. Antibacterial action of all prepared compounds have investigated against 5 type of bacterial strain and results revealed that metal complex have advanced antibacterial action than pure ligand. Cu complex showed better capacity to inhibit all bacterial strains.^[33] H. A. Elbadawy et al. have prepared 2 azo-Schiff base compounds L_{16} and L_{17} by the interaction of 4-((3-formyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)diazanyl) benzenesulfonamide with o-aminophenol and o-amino-thiophenol respectively. Their metal complexes have designed with Cu(II) and Zn(II) metals. All the designed compounds have checked for their antimicrobial potential in opposed to *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram positive bacteria) and *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative bacteria). The examined compounds were found to have antibacterial activities against the majority of the tested pathogens, and the pure ligand was also proven to be active against both gram positive and negative bacteria.^[34] I. Waziri et al. have designed a ligand (Z)-2-[(4-nitrobenzylidene)amino]phenol (L_{18}) and its metal complex have prepared with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) metal ions. Antibacterial activity of all the prepared compounds have investigated and the results showed that designed complexes have advanced disinfectant property than pure ligand.^[35] K. B. Sakhare et al. have synthesized a Schiff ligand (L_{19}) and Transition metal complex have prepared with Ni(II), Mn(II), Cu(II), Co(II), VO(II) and Zn(II) metal ions. Bioactivity of all the prepared compounds in opposed to *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa* have investigated and the results concluded that all designed complexes displayed higher activity than pure ligand.^[36] Z. H. Mohammed et al.

have prepared a azo-Schiff ligand (L₂₀) and its Metal complexes have prepared with Cu(II), Zn(II) metal ions. All the prepared compounds have investigated for their antibacterial activity on Mueller Hinton agar plate against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Findings of the test showed suppressive effect of metal complex and ligand.^[37] Jenan F. Hassan et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand (L₂₁) by the reaction of cephalixin and vanillin. Its metal complexes have prepared with Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd metal chlorides. All compounds have investigated against *S. aureus* and *E. Coli*. Results revealed that Co complex have higher activity than pure ligand against *S. aureus*.^[38] A. Z. El-Sonbati et al. have synthesized a Schiff ligand (L₂₂) using 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine. Its metal complexes have designed with Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), and UO₂(II) metal ions. All compounds have tested for their biological activity against *P. aeruginosa*, *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, and *S. aureus*. All compounds have variable activity at different concentration.^[39]

Figure No. 2: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 3: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₉	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	N-benzylidene-isonicotinohydrazide
L ₁₀	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄ SO ₄	4,5-Methylenedioxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone
L ₁₁	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NBrO ₃	5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde-β-alanine
L ₁₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	6,6 ¹ -((1,2-phenylene-bis(azaneylylidene))bis(methaneylylidene))bis(2-ethoxyphenol)
L ₁₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	6,6 ¹ -((pyridine-2,6-diylbis(azaneylylidene))-bis(methaneylylidene))bis(2-ethoxyphenol)
L ₁₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	4-((3-ethoxy-2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)pyrimidin-2(1H)one
L ₁₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	[N'-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl)-4-methyl benzohydrazide]
L ₁₆	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	4-(((4-hydroxy-3-(((2-hydroxyphenyl)imino)methyl)phenyl) diazenyl)benzenesulfonamide)]
L ₁₇	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	4-(((4-hydroxy-3-(((2-mercaptophenyl)imino)methyl) phenyl) diazenyl)benzene sulfonamide)
L ₁₈	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	(Z)-2-[(4-Nitrobenzylidene)Amino] Phenol
L ₁₉	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ O ₄	4-Bromo-2-((E)-((2-hydroxyphenyl)imino)methyl-6-((E)-(3-nitrophenyl)diazinyl)phenyl
L ₂₀	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₂	N,N'-bis[(E)-1-(4-ethoxyphenyl)diazinyl]-N,N'-bis(benzylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine
L ₂₁	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₆ S	(E)-N-[(7R)-3-methyl-7-(α-D-phenylglycylamino)-3-cephem-4-carboxylidene]-4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylideneamine.
L ₂₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	(E)-2-[(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)amino]-3-hydroxypyridine

Table No. 4: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	9.50 mm	Kanamycin
Cu-L ₉	<i>E. coli</i>	-	14.5 mm	
L ₁₀	<i>S. mutans</i>	1000 µg/mL	-	-
Pd-L ₁₀	<i>S. mutans</i>	500 µg/mL	-	
L ₁₁	<i>S. mutans</i>	>1000 µg/mL	-	
Pd-L ₁₁	<i>S. mutans</i>	62.5 µg/mL	-	Garamycin, Imipenem
L ₁₂	<i>E. coli</i>	No activity	-	
L ₁₃	<i>E. coli</i>	No activity	-	
L ₁₄	<i>E. coli</i>	25.92 µg/mL	6mm	Tetracycline
L ₁₅	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	6mm	
Cu-L ₁₅	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	18mm	Gentamicin
L ₁₆	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	13mm	
L ₁₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	13mm	
Zn-L ₁₆	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	-	12mm	
Zn-L ₁₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	13mm	
L ₁₈	<i>B. subtilis</i>	62.5µg/mL	-	ciprofloxacin
Ni-L ₁₈	<i>B. subtilis</i>	3.9µg/mL	-	
L ₁₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	8mm	tetracycline
Mn-L ₁₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	22mm	
L ₂₀	<i>E.coli</i>	250 µg/mL	8mm	-
Zn-L ₂₀	<i>S. aureus</i>	250 µg/mL	20mm	
L ₂₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	11-20mm	-

Co-L ₂₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	>20mm	penicillin G
L ₂₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	100 µg/mL	6 mm	
Ni-L ₂₂	<i>E.coli</i>	50 µg/mL	11 mm	

S. D. Oladipo et al. have designed 2 Schiff bases (E)-N-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)methanimine (L₂₃), (E)-4-(((4-bromophenyl)imino)methyl)phenol (L₂₄). Both compounds have observed for their antimicrobial potential against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*. The findings revealed that both compounds exhibited good activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and have no activity against remaining two bacterial strains.^[40] D. N. Ali et al. have synthesized 3 Schiff ligands namely, 2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]-4-{(E)-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]methyl}phenol (L₂₅), 4-{(E)-[(4-ethylphenyl)imino]methyl}-2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]phenol (L₂₆) and 4-{(E)-[(4-hydroxyphenyl)imino]methyl}-2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]phenol (L₂₇) (Figure No. 3 & Table No. 5). Every formulated ligand have examined for antimicrobial potential in opposed to *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The findings revealed that all ligands exhibited significant activity. Presence of hydroxy group in ligand 27 made it efficient in inhibitory action against bacteria.^[41] U. P. S. Prabhakar et al. have successfully manufactured a Schiff ligand (L₂₈) and its Complexes have synthesized by combining Zinc(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) ions with ligand. The germicidal potential test of all compounds have performed in opposed to various bacterial species. Results conclude that the coordination of metals with ligand results in enhanced antimicrobial properties than the uncoordinated, free ligands (Table No. 6). All compounds, showed the most revealing inhibitory activity in opposed to *S. aureus* at 200 µg/mL and the lowest suppressing activity opposed to *E. coli* at 100 µg/ml.^[42] Edebi N. Vaikosen et al. have prepared synthesized 4 Schiff ligands by the reaction of para aminophenol with benzaldehyde (L₂₉), anisaldehyde (L₃₀), 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (L₃₁), and cinnamaldehyde (L₃₂). All ligands showed antibacterial activity against *E. coli*. Ligand L₂₉, L₃₀, L₃₁ showed activity against *S. aureus*. The Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) for ligand L₂₉, L₃₀, L₃₂ have found 125ug/ml, 500ug/ml, and 250ug/ml respectively.^[43]

Figure No. 3: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 5: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₂₃	C ₁₃ H ₈ BrCl ₂ N	(E)-N-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(2,6-dichlorophenyl) methanimine
L ₂₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ BrNO	(E)-4-(((4-bromophenyl)imino)methyl)phenol
L ₂₅	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]-4-[(E)-(4-methylphenyl)imino]methyl phenol
L ₂₆	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	4-[(E)-(4-ethylphenyl)imino]-methyl-2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]phenol
L ₂₇	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	4-[(E)-(4-hydroxyphenyl)imino]methyl-2-[(4-methylphenyl)diazenyl]phenol
L ₂₈	C ₁₃ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂	2,4-dichloro-6-[(2-hydroxy-phenylimino)-methyl]-phenol
L ₂₉	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO	4-(benzylideneamino)phenol
L ₃₀	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	4-[(4-methoxybenzylidene)amino]phenol
L ₃₁	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	4-[(4-nitrobenzylidene)amino]phenol
L ₃₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ NO	4-[(3-phenylprop-2-enylidene)amino]phenol

Table No. 6: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	MBC	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₂₃	<i>S. aureus</i>	2000µg/mL	3000µg/mL	-	-
L ₂₄	<i>K. Pneumonia</i>	1000µg/mL	3000µg/mL	-	
L ₂₅	<i>E.coli</i>	50000µg/mL	-	24mm	-
L ₂₆	<i>E.coli</i>	50000µg/mL	-	21mm	
L ₂₇	<i>S. aureus</i>	50000µg/mL	-	26mm	
L ₂₈ -ZnCl ₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	200µg/mL	-	17mm	ciprofloxacin

L ₂₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	62.5µg/mL	-	8mm	-
L ₃₀	<i>S. aureus</i>	62.5µg/mL	-	8mm	
L ₃₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	62.5µg/mL	-	7mm	
L ₃₂	<i>E. coli</i>	62.5µg/mL	-	7mm	

Sivan Arulmozhi et al. have prepared transition metal complexes using Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Mn(II) with Schiff base azine namely, 2-(I-((I-(1H-pyrrol-2-yl)methylene)hydrazineylidene) methyl)phenol (L₃₃). Biological activity test of all compounds have done in opposed to bacteria like *E. faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and compared their effects to the antibiotic ciprofloxacin. Among all compounds, copper complex have shown moderate antibacterial activity. Out of all the bacteria tested, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* responded the most to the metal complexes. Also, the antibacterial effect became stronger as the amount of the complexes increased.^[44] A. A. Olanrewaju et al. have prepared three Schiff bases namely, (Z)-2-(4-cyanobenzylidene)-N-methylhydrazine carbothioamide (L₃₄), (Z)-2-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzylidene)-N-methylhydrazinecarbothioamide (L₃₅), (Z)-2-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)-N-methylhydrazinecarbothioamide (L₃₆) (Figure No. 4 & Table No. 7). All formulated compounds have confirmed for their germicidal activity in opposed to *B. cereus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Findings exposed that every designed compound have activity towards tested bacterial strains (Table No. 8). Molecular docking confirmed the biological efficiency of compounds.^[45] M. Al-Fakeh et al. have prepared metal complexes using MnCl₂·4H₂O, CoCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O, CrCl₃·6H₂O, PdCl₂ metal salts, 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine and with a Schiff ligand 2-((E)-((4-((E)benzylidene)amino) phenyl)imino)methyl) naphthalene-1-ol (L₃₇). All compounds have tested for their potential against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*. Pd and Cu complex showed highest activity and Mn complex showed least antibacterial activity.^[46] R. O. Awolope et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand 4,4'-{ethane-1,2-diylbis[nitrile(Z)methylidene]}bis(2-methoxyphenol) (L₃₈). Its metal complexes have designed with Co, Cu, Ni, Zr, V, and U metals. Antibacterial property have evaluated against *S. aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *P. aeruginosa* and results revealed that metal complexes have strong to moderate activity.^[47] S. Y. Hussaini et al. have prepared metal complexes with Co(II), Ni(II) metal ions and with Schiff ligand (L₃₉). Antibacterial potential of prepared compounds have evaluated against *S. aureus* and *Salmonella typhias*. Results revealed that all compounds have potential to kill tested bacteria and all compounds have lower activity than gentamicin.^[48] I. K. Aminu et al. have

synthesized a ligand 2-hydroxybenzalidene-1-naphthylamine (L₄₀) and its metal complexes with Mn(II) and Ni(II) metal ions. Antibacterial activity test for all designed compounds have performed against *S. typhi* and *S. pneumoniae*. Findings revealed that all compounds exhibited moderate activity.^[49] S. A. Ahmed et al. have prepared a ligand namely, potassium 2-(4-(4-(dimethylamino) benzylidene)amino)-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazole-3-ylidene) amino)-3-methylbitanoate (L₄₁) and its complexes with Cu, Ni, Zn and Co metals. All compounds have investigated for their antibacterial activity against *S. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureuginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae*. Results revealed that all compounds have antibacterial activity and every tested compound revealed lower activity than standard drug Amoxicillin.^[50]

Figure No. 4: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 7: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₃₃	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	2-(ϵ -((ϵ -(1H-pyrrol-2-yl)methylene)hydrazineylidene)methyl)phenol
L ₃₄	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	(Z)-2-(4-cyanobenzylidene)-N-methylhydrazinecarbothioamide
L ₃₅	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	(Z)-2-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzylidene)-N-methylhydrazinecarbothioamide
L ₃₆	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	(Z)-2-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)-N-methylhydrazinecarbothioamide
L ₃₇	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	2-(ϵ -((ϵ -(4-(benzylidene)amino)phenyl)imino)methyl)naphthalene-1-ol
L ₃₈	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	4,4'-{ethane-1,2-diylbis[trile(Z)methyllylidene]}bis(2-methoxyphenol)
L ₃₉	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄	ϵ -2-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)hydrazono-1-phenylethanol

L ₄₀	C17H13NO	2-hydroxybenzalidene-1-naphthylamine
L ₄₁	C25H30KN5O2	potassium 2-(4-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)amino)-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazole-3-ylidene)amino)-3-methylbitanoate

Table No. 8: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
Cu(L ₃₃)(bpy)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	-	13.3mm	ciprofloxacin
L ₃₄	<i>B. cereus</i>	-	10.0mm	Streptomycin, Gentamycin
L ₃₅	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	21.0mm	
L ₃₆	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	10.0mm	
Pd-L ₃₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	29.60mm	Gentamycin
L ₃₈	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	8mm	Neomycin
Zr-L ₃₈	<i>E. faecalis</i>	-	17mm	
L ₃₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	12500µg/mL	20mm	Gentamicin
Ni-L ₃₉	<i>S. aureus</i>	12500µg/mL	20mm	
L ₄₀	<i>S. typhi</i>	-	10mm	Gentamycin
Ni-L ₄₀	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	-	13mm	
L ₄₁	<i>S. aureus</i>	60µg/mL	-	Amoxicillin
Zn-(L ₄₁) ₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	50µg/mL	-	

Ali M. Hassan et al. have prepared metal complexes by both conventional and microwave method with transition metals (Cobalt, Copper, Manganese, Nickel, Zirconium and Zinc metals) and a Schiff ligand 2-Methoxy-6-((E)-((4-((E)-phenyldiazenyl)phenyl)imino)methyl)phenol (L₄₂) (Figure No. 5 & Table No. 9). When tested against bacteria, the Schiff base alone have shown no effect while, the metal complexes showed much stronger antimicrobial activity. All the prepared compound have examined for germicidal activity in opposed to *P. aeruginosa*, *Bacillus*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*. Structure antimicrobial activity relationship revealed that compounds which contain both hydroxy and amino group have maximum activity.^[51] B. Kenan et al. have created metal complexes by the reaction of Cobalt(II), Iron(II), Palladium(II), Ruthenium(II) metals with a Schiff base ligand ((E)-methyl 2-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-6-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothieno[2,3-c]pyridine-3-carboxylate) (L₄₃). Metal complexes have investigated for their inhibitory capacity in opposed to some bacterial strain like Gram-negative types (*Enterobacter aerogenes*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), Gram-positive types (*Bacillus subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *Bacillus megaterium*). The findings exposed that every formulated complex displayed greater germicidal property than pure ligand alone. Cobalt complex showed highest antibacterial activity (Table No. 10).^[52] S. Sani et al. have prepared a Schiff base (L₄₄) and its transition metal complexes have prepared with Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Co(II). Antibacterial activity of all compounds have verified in opposed to *E. coli* and other bacterial strains. Results

revealed that complexes have advanced germicidal activity compared to pure Schiff ligand.^[53] Venkatesh Rangaswamy et al. have prepared a Schiff base (L₄₅) using 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde and 4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine. Its metal complexes have prepared with Ni, Zn, Cd metals. Antibacterial activity test have performed against *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis*, *S. pneumoniae*, *B. subtilis*. All compounds showed activity towards every tested bacteria. Ni and Zn complex showed no activity towards *E. Coli*.^[54]

Figure No. 5: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 9: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₄₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	2-Methoxy-6-((4-phenyldiazenyl)phenyl)imino)methylphenol
L ₄₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	(6-methyl-2-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-6-methyl 4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothieno[2,3-c]pyridine-3-carboxylate)
L ₄₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	N,N'-bis(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)benzene-1,2-diamine
L ₄₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₆	N,N'-bis(5-methoxy-2-hydroxybenzylidene)-4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine

Table No. 10: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₄₂	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	14mm	-
Zn-L ₄₂	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	14mm	
L ₄₃	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	-	12mm	Erythromycin, Ampicillin/Sulbactam, Amikacin, Rifampicin,
Co-L ₄₃	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	23mm	
L ₄₄	<i>E. coli</i>	15000µg/mL	10mm	Ciprofloxacin
[Zn(L ₄₄)]·2H ₂ O	<i>E. coli</i>	15000µg/mL	13mm	
L ₄₅	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	9mm	Ciprofloxacin
Cd-L ₄₅	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	-	9mm	

N. P. Yahaya et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand 3-aminophenol Benzaldehyde (L₄₆) and its Metal complex have prepared through the reaction between Schiff ligand, ampicillin and Fe,

Co, Mn, Cu transition metals in 1:1:1 molar ratio. Antibacterial activity of all prepared compounds have investigated by disc diffusion procedure against *staphylococcus aureus*, *staphylococcus pyogenes*, *salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli*. Findings of the test concluded that all the designed metal complexes have significant antibacterial activity.^[55] T.A. Nibila et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand (E)-2-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-N-methyl-N-phenylhydrazine carbothioamide (L₄₇) (Figure No. 6 & Table No. 11) and its complexes have designed with Co, Ni and Cu metal chlorides. Antimicrobial activity test have performed against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*.^[56] Jitendra N. Borase et al. have prepared a ligand namely, 4-((E)-(4-methylpyridin-2-ylimino)methyl) benzene-1,3-diol (L₄₈). Its metal complexes have prepared with Fe(III), Co(III), Cu(II), and Ni(II) metal ions. Antibacterial activity test have performed against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*. Results revealed that Cu complex have highest activity against *E.coli*.^[57] S. M. El-Gamasy et al. have synthesized a Schiff ligand (L₄₉) and its metal complexes have designed with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Cr(II) and Zn(II) metal ions. All compounds have investigated for their activity against *S. pneumonine*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. Cu complex exhibited highest activity against *B. subtilis* (Table No. 12).^[58]

Figure No. 6: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 11: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₄₆	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ON	3-aminophenol Benzaldehyde
L ₄₇	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	€-2-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-N-methyl-N-phenyl hydrazine carbothioamide
L ₄₈	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	4-(€-(4-methylpyridin-2-ylimino)methyl)benzene -1,3-diol
L ₄₉	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	N,N'-bis(benzylidene)-o-phenylenediamine-2,2'-dihydrazide

Table No. 12: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₄₆	<i>S. aureus</i>	50000 µg/mL	15mm	Ceftriaxone, Subactam
Cu(L ₄₆)(Ampi)	<i>E. Coil</i>	50000 µg/mL	22mm	
L ₄₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	20mm	Gentamycin
Cu-L ₄₇	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	25mm	
Cu-L ₄₈	<i>E.coli</i>	-	10.44mm	Chloramphenicol
L ₄₉	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	30.3mm	Linezolid
Cu-L ₄₉	<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	19.8mm	

F. A. Abdulsayid et al. have formulated a Schiff base ligand (L₅₀) and its complexes with TM metals have designed with Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Pb(II) metal ions. All prepared compounds have explored for germicidal activity in opposed to *E. Coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella* bacterial strains. Compounds showed their activity only against *E. Coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*.^[59] Usman B et al. have used a microwave irradiation method to prepare a Schiff base ligand €-N-benzylidene acetamide (L₅₁). Its metal complex with Co and Ni metals have prepared. Antibacterial activity of synthesized compounds have tested in opposed to *P. Aenoginosa* and *E. Coli*. The findings revealed that metal complex have better activity than pure Schiff ligand but have less activity than amoxicillin (a reference drug).^[60] S. E. A. El-Razek et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand (L₅₂) (Figure No. 7 & Table No. 13) and its metal complexes have prepared with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Bi(III), and Zn(II) metal ions. Antibacterial activity of all prepared compounds have investigated against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*. Complex made with CuSO₄.5H₂O and with ligand showed highest activity against gram positive bacteria. Complex made from Co(oAc)₂.4H₂O and ligand have showed high zone of inhibition against gram negative bacteria.^[61] Sajjad H. Sumrra et al. have prepared 2-[[[5-[[1-(5-methylfuran-2-yl)ethylidene]amino]-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]imino]methyl]phenol (L₅₃). Its metal complexes have designed with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), and Cr(III) metals as chloride and, VO(IV) as sulfate with ligand (L₅₃) in 1:2 (M:L) molar ratio. Antibacterial test have performed against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *N. gonorrhoea* and *P. syringae* bacterial strains. Copper complex have highest activity among all tested compounds (Table No. 14).^[62] Ifeanyi E. Otuokere et al. have prepared a Schiff ligand 4-{{€-phenylmethylidene]amino}-N-(1,3-thiazol 2-yl)benzene sulfonamide (PTBS) (L₅₄) and its complex with Ni metal ion. Antibacterial activity investigation against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *E.coli* and *P. aeruginosa* have done. Metal complex showed higher activity than pure ligand.^[63]

Figure No. 7: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 13: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₅₀	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ NO ₄	€-2-[(3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]-4-methyl pentanoic acid
L ₅₁	C ₉ H ₉ NO	€-N-benzylideneacetamide
L ₅₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂	N,N'-bis[(2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]benzene-1,4-diyl diguanidine
L ₅₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂	2-[[[5-[[1-(5-methylfuran-2-yl)ethylidene]amino]-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]imino]methyl] phenol
L ₅₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	4-[[€-phenylmethylidene]amino]-N-(1,3-thiazol-2-yl) benzene sulfonamide

Table No. 14: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₅₀	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	22mm	-
L ₅₁	<i>E. coli</i>	25000 µg/mL	-	Amoxicilin
Ni-L ₅₁	<i>E. coli</i>	12500 µg/mL	-	
L ₅₂	<i>p. aeruginosa</i>	-	14mm	Neomycin
Cu-L ₅₂	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	23mm	
L ₅₃	<i>E. coli</i>	-	5mm	Kanamycin
Cu-L ₅₃	<i>N. gonorrhoea</i>	-	10mm	
L ₅₄	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	17.00mm	-
Ni-L ₅₄	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	20.00mm	

M. Pervaiz et al. have synthesized a Schiff base (L₅₅) by the reaction of salicylaldehyde with leucine amino acid in a basic solution. Metal complexes have made by combining the ligand with Copper and Cadmium, Cobalt, Manganese metals. Antimicrobial activity assay have performed in opposed to bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *S. aureus*. The findings concluded that complexes displayed significantly greater antibacterial activity in contrast to the pure ligand alone.^[64] H.M. Vinusha et al. have created a novel Schiff ligand (L₅₆) from 5-amino-4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3-thiol and 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzaldehyde.

Prepared ligand have used to formulate metal complex with Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), and Ni(II) metals. Antibacterial activity assay have performed against 9 food pathogens (three Gram positive bacteria – *B. cereus*, *M. luteus*, *S. aureus* and six Gram negative bacteria- *K. pneumonia*, *E. aerogenes*, *E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. enteritidis*). Amoxicillin drug have used as standard reference as antibiotic agent. MIC value for pure ligand and all the metal complexes have calculated. Results showed that metal complex displayed advanced antimicrobial efficiency over pure ligand. Zn complex exhibited the maximum antimicrobial potential between all tested compounds.^[65] E. Osoikhia et al. have prepared a Schiff base (L₅₇) Salicylidene-tyrosine by the reaction of L-tyrosine and salicylaldehyde (Figure No. 8 & Table No. 15). Transition metal complex have synthesized by taking Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II) metals and Schiff base in 1:1 ratio. Metal complexes have examined for their antimicrobial potential in opposed to *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*. Findings concluded that Cu complex have the maximum efficiency to all variants.^[66] M. S. Hossain et al. have manufactured a Schiff ligand (L₅₈) from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 2-amino pyridine. Its metal complex have designed with Fe(II), Mn(II), Cd(II) and Co(II) metals. Designed compounds have verified for germicidal potential in opposed to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Acetobacter aceti*. Almost all metal complexes have expressed their better activity than pure ligand.^[67] N. Mahalaksmi et al. have synthesized a Schiff ligand (L₅₉) by the reaction of pentane-2,4-dione, 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde and 4,5-dichloro o-phenylenediamine. Its metal complex have prepared with VO(IV), Ni(II) and Cu(II) metal ions. Biological activity of synthesized compounds have tested for different bacterial strains and the results showed that activity of compounds have increased as the concentration of compounds increased (Table No. 16).^[68]

Figure No. 8: Structure of Ligands.

Table No. 15: Formula and IUPAC name of ligands.

Ligand	Formula	IUPAC name of Ligand
L ₅₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NO ₃	€-2-[(2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]-4-methyl pentanoic acid
L ₅₆	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	4-(((5-mercapto-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)imino)methyl)-2-methoxyphenol
L ₅₇	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ NO ₄	2-[(2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoic acid
L ₅₈	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	€-4-[(pyridine-2-ylimino)methyl]phenol
L ₅₉	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrCl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	€-4,5-dichloro-2-[(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino]benzene-1,2-diyl bis(pentan-2,4-dione imine)

Table No. 16: Data Of Antimicrobial Study.

Compounds	Strains	MIC value	Inhibition zone	Standard drug
L ₅₅	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	6.74mm	Rifampicin
Cd- L ₅₅	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	12.25mm	
L ₅₆	<i>E. aerogenes</i>	-	11.04mm	Amoxicillin
Zn- L ₅₆	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	25.87mm	
L ₅₇	<i>S. aureus</i>	1000µg/mL	14mm	Ciprofloxacin
[Cu(L ₅₇)(H ₂ O) ₃].H ₂ O	<i>S. aureus</i>	1000µg/mL	28mm	
L ₅₈	<i>E. Coli</i>	-	11mm	Ampicillin
Co-L ₅₈	<i>E. Coli</i>	-	13mm	
L ₅₉	<i>E. Coli</i>	-	18mm	Ciprofloxacin
Cu-L ₅₉	<i>Bacillus</i>	-	20mm	

DISCUSSION

A. Mechanism of action for metal complexes

1. Tweedy's chelation theory

According to Tweedy's chelation theory, when a metal ion binds with a ligand to form a complex, the polarity of the metal ion decreases. This happens because the electrons become more spread out over the whole chelate structure and some positive charge of the metal is shared with the donor atoms of the ligand. As a result, the metal complex becomes more lipophilic, meaning it can pass more easily through the lipid membrane of bacterial cells. Chelation also changes the electronic properties and charge distribution of the metal complex, which can increase its biological activity. Due to orbital overlap and charge sharing between the metal ion and ligand, the complex can cross the hydrophobic barriers of microbial cells more effectively than the free ligand. Once inside the cell, the complex may bind strongly with bacterial enzymes and block important metal-binding sites, which disturbs normal enzyme function. Therefore, metal complexes usually show better antibacterial activity than uncoordinated Schiff base ligands.

2. Cell Membrane Penetration and Disruption

The increased lipophilic nature of metal complexes helps them pass through bacterial cell membranes more easily and enter the cell effectively. Inside the cell, they interact with membrane proteins and phospholipids, which damages the membrane structure and increases its permeability. As a result, important cellular materials such as ions and proteins leak out, and the membrane loses its normal potential. These changes disturb normal cell functions and finally lead to the death of the bacterial cell.

3. Enzyme Inhibition

Metal complexes can interact with enzymes by binding to functional groups like $-SH$, $-NH_2$, and $-COOH$ present in amino acids. This binding blocks the active sites of enzymes and changes their normal structure. As a result, important metabolic and respiratory processes, including ATP production, are disturbed, which affects bacterial growth and eventually leads to cell death.

4. Interaction with Bacterial DNA

Some Schiff base metal complexes can directly bind with bacterial DNA by inserting between DNA base pairs, attaching to DNA grooves, or interacting with the phosphate backbone through electrostatic forces. These interactions disturb important processes like DNA replication and transcription, which prevents proper cell division and protein synthesis. As a result, the growth and survival of bacteria are inhibited, contributing to the antibacterial activity of these complexes.

5. Generation of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS)

Transition metal complexes, especially those containing redox-active metals such as $Cu(II)$, can promote the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) like superoxide radicals (O_2^-), hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). These reactive species create oxidative stress inside bacterial cells by damaging important biomolecules such as DNA, proteins, and lipid membranes. This damage disturbs normal cellular functions and eventually causes bacterial cell death.

6. Protein Denaturation and Metal Ion Interaction

Metal ions released from metal complexes, or present in equilibrium with them, can strongly bind to thiol ($-SH$) groups in bacterial proteins. This interaction can denature the proteins,

reduce enzyme activity, and damage important cellular structures. As a result, normal cellular functions are permanently disturbed, leading to irreversible damage in the bacterial cell.

7. Synergistic Effect of Ligand and Metal Ion

Unlike free ligands, metal complexes show a synergistic effect where the ligand helps improve solubility and targeting ability, while the metal ion enhances reactivity and interaction with biological systems. Because of this combined action, metal complexes often display a broader range of antibacterial activity, lower minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), and better overall effectiveness.

B. Comparative Study of Biological Activity for Different Metal Complexes

The difference in antibacterial activity of Schiff base complexes containing Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), and Zn(II) is mainly due to variations in their ionic size, redox properties, and coordination geometry. Among these metals, Cu(II) complexes usually show the highest antibacterial activity because they form strong chelates, have a suitable ionic radius, and can easily take part in redox reactions that produce reactive oxygen species, leading to greater damage to microbial cells. Ni(II) complexes generally exhibit moderate to good activity because of their stable coordination behavior, while Co(II) complexes show moderate effects due to their lower redox ability. On the other hand, Zn(II) complexes often show the lowest activity since zinc is redox inactive and commonly forms tetrahedral structures, which reduce their interaction with biological targets. Overall, the antibacterial activity generally follows the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Zn(II), depending on both structural and physicochemical factors.

CONCLUSION

The review verifies that Schiff base ligands derived from benzaldehyde display moderate antibacterial properties, which are considerably improved upon complexation with transition metal ions due to synergistic interactions between the metal and the ligand. These complexes exhibit enhanced lipophilicity, facilitating improved penetration through bacterial cell membranes and stronger interactions with critical biomolecular targets within microbial cells. As a result, they exhibit a wider range of activity and reduced inhibitory concentrations in comparison to the free ligands. In general, these metal complexes are promising options for creating effective antibacterial agents, especially in tackling the increasing problem of antimicrobial resistance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to GCRC for providing the necessary resources and guidance in completing the review paper.

FUNDING

We sincerely thank to university grant commission (UGC) for financial support.

REFERENCES

1. Dougan G, Baker S. Salmonella enterica serovar Typhi and the pathogenesis of typhoid fever. *Annu Rev Microbiol*, 2014; 68(1): 317-336.
2. Worley MJ. Salmonella bloodstream infections. *Trop. Med. Infect. Dis.*, 2023; 8(11): 487.
3. Minasyan H. Sepsis: mechanisms of bacterial injury to the patient. *Scand J Trauma Resusc. Emerg. Med.*, 2019; 27(1): 19.
4. Browne AJ, Kashef Hamadani BH, Kumaran EAP, Rao P, Longbottom J, Harriss E, Moore CE, et al. Drug-resistant enteric fever worldwide, 1990 to 2018: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Med.*, 2020; 18(1): 1.
5. Al-Hazmi GAA, Melha KSA, El-Metwaly NM, Althagafi I, Shaaban F, Zaky R. Green synthesis approach for Fe(III), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Ni(II)-Schiff base complexes, spectral, conformational, MOE docking and biological studies. *Appl. Organomet Chem.*, 2020; 34(3): 5403.
6. Frei A, Verderosa AD, Elliott AG, Zuegg J, Blaskovich MA. Metals to combat antimicrobial resistance. *Nat. Rev. Chem.*, 2023; 7(3): 202-224.
7. Carpio ED, Hernandez L, Lubes V, Francisco J, Cerecetto H, Scalese G, Gambino D, Romero AH. Current developments of metal- and metalloid-based quinoline compounds as leishmanicidal agents. *Front Chem.*, 2025; 13: 1586044.
8. Wang C, Wei X, Zhong L, Chan CL, Li H, Sun H. Metal-based approaches for the fight against antimicrobial resistance: mechanisms, opportunities, and challenges. *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 2025; 147(15): 12361-12380.
9. Scalese G, Kostenkova K, Crans DC, Gambino D. Metallomics and other omics approaches in antiparasitic metal-based drug research. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.*, 2022; 67: 102127.
10. Ram R, Verma KK, Solanki K, Bhojak N. Microwave assisted synthesis, spectral and antibacterial investigations on complexes of Co(II) with amide containing ligands. *Int. J New Technol. Sci. Eng.*, 2015; 2(6): 92-100.

11. Verma KK, Nirwan N, Singh R, Bhojak N. Microwave assisted synthesis, characterisation and biological activities of Cu(II) complexes of few thiosemicarbazone ligands. *J Sci. Res.*, 2023; 15(1): 275-283.
12. Verma KK, Verma SK. Microwave assisted synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and antimicrobial activities of Co(II) complexes containing biologically active thiosemicarbazone derivatives. *Chem. Res. J.*, 2021; 6(5): 80-86.
13. Xia L, Xia Y, Huang L, Xiao X, Lou H, Liu T, Pan W, Luo H. Benzaldehyde Schiff bases regulation to the metabolism, hemolysis, and virulence genes expression in vitro and their structure–microbicidal activity relationship. *Eur. J Med. Chem.*, 2015; 97: 83-93.
14. Zhang HJ, Qin X, Liu K, Zhu DD, Wang XM, Zhu HL. Synthesis, antibacterial activities and molecular docking studies of Schiff bases derived from N-(2/4-benzaldehyde-amino) phenyl-N'-phenyl-thiourea. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2011; 19(18): 5708-5715.
15. Matar SA, Talib WH, Mustafa MS, Mubarak MS, AlDamen MA. Synthesis, characterization, and antimicrobial activity of Schiff bases derived from benzaldehydes and 3,3'-diaminodipropylamine. *Arab J Chem.*, 2015; 8(6): 850-857.
16. Kasare MS, Dhavan PP, Shaikh AHI, Jadhav BL, Pawar SD. Novel Schiff base scaffolds derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5-(phenyldiazenyl) benzaldehyde: synthesis, antibacterial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. *J Mol. Recognit.*, 2022; 35(9): 2976.
17. Luo H, Xia YF, Sun BF, Huang LR, Wang XH, Lou H, Zhu X, Pan W, Zhang X. Synthesis and evaluation of in vitro antibacterial and antitumor activities of novel N,N-disubstituted Schiff bases. *Biochem. Res. Int.*, 2017; 2017(1): 6257240.
18. Waheed EJ. Synthesis, characterization and biological activity of new ligand derived from 4-(dimethylamino)benzaldehyde and nano copper complex. *Baghdad Sci. J.*, 2025; 22(4): 1085-1101.
19. Malav R, Ray S. Recent advances in the synthesis and versatile applications of transition metal complexes featuring Schiff base ligands. *RSC Adv.*, 2025; 15(28): 22889-22914.
20. Veg E, Hashmi K, Ahmad MI, Joshi S, Khan AR, Khan T. Some biological applications and mechanistic insights of benzaldehyde-substituted thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes: a review. *Nat. Sci.*, 2025; 5: 70005.
21. Rana MS, Rayhan NMA, Emad AH, Hossain MI, Shah MM, Zahan MKE, Hossen MF, Asraf MA. Salicylaldehyde-based Schiff bases and their transition metal complexes: an overview on synthesis and biological activities. *J Coord. Chem.*, 2025; 78(9): 937-1006.

22. Alshrefe A, Waheed EJ, Hussein MS. Synthesis and characterization of a new Schiff base ligand derived from o-vanillin with some transition metal complexes and study of antimicrobial activity. *Bull. Pharm. Sci. Assiut. Univ.*, 2026; 49(1): 205-218.
23. Sakhare DT. Synthesis, characterization of some novel Schiff base ligand metal complexes: spectral, thermal analysis, XRD and antimicrobial studies. *Int. J Chem. Res.*, 2026; 35-42.
24. Thakkar KJ, Patel RJ, Chauhan RR, Thakor PM, Patel JD, Patel HV, Thakkar AB, Mansuri JA, Kunjadiya AP. Design and bio evaluation of Schiff base and their metal complexes: a green route to potential anticancer agents. *ACS Omega*, 2026; 11(7): 11721-11738.
25. Wahdan KM, Mandour HSA, El-Ghamry HA, El-Gamil MM, Khedr AM. Structure elucidation and evaluation of the antimicrobial and antitumor activities of 5-methylthiazole-based Schiff base and its metal chelates. *Sci. Rep.*, 2026.
26. Elaaraj I, Oulidi O, Er Raouan S, Bouymajane A, Nakkabi A, Saad IK, Cacciola F, El Moualij N, Fahim M. Synthesis, characterization, and antioxidant/antibacterial activities of new mono- and bi-nuclear complexes of Zn(II), Cu(II), and Co(II) based on the ligand 4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)-N,N-dimethylaniline. *Biointerface Res. Appl. Chem.*, 2026; 16(1): 1-25.
27. Kumar S. Synthesis, characterization and biological applications of Schiff base capped CdS nanoparticles prepared via an ultrasonically assisted green chemical method., 2026.
28. Abdel-Rahman LH, Abou El-Ezz D, Abdel-Mawgoud MM, Shehata MR, El-Remaily MAAA, Abdel-Hameed M, Mohamed SK. Synthesis and biological evaluation of ibuprofen/o-vanillin Schiff base complexes with anti-inflammatory, anti-proliferative and anti-SARS-CoV-19 activities. *Sci. Rep.*, 2026.
29. El-Hakeem GA, Gouda GA, Abd El-Rahem KA, Hosny S. Comprehensive experimental and theoretical investigations of novel triazine Schiff base metal complexes: spectroscopic, electrochemical, DNA interaction, in vitro cytotoxicity, antimicrobial and in silico studies. *BMC Chem.*, 2026.
30. Islam MA, Zahan MKE, Tasnim F, Hossain MS, Asraf MA. Experimental and computational insights into antibacterial and antioxidant properties of metal complexes with isoniazid-based Schiff base ligands. *J Mol. Struct.*, 2025; 1324: 140916.
31. de Oliveira Amaral L, Santiago LR, Ferreira WV, da Silva JDS, Bortoluzzi AJ, Marques MB, Costa MJF, Sette-de-Souza PH, Soares SM. Novel palladium(II) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 4,5-methylenedioxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde and 5-bromo-2-

- hydroxybenzaldehyde as potential antimicrobial agents: synthesis, characterization and studies in vitro. *J Mol. Struct.*, 2025; 1328: 141403.
32. Ahmed AG, Mohammed HA, Mustafea ZM, Fetouh HA. Facile and rapid synthesis of a new series of Schiff bases: characterization and evaluation of the physicochemical properties and biological activities. *New J Chem.*, 2025; 49(31): 13357-13368.
33. Waheed EJ. Synthesis, characterization and anticancer activity of some metal complexes of new ligand derived from 4-methylbenzohydrazide with computational studies. *Iraqi. J Pharm. Sci.*, 2025; 34(2): 122-143.
34. Elbadawy HA, Eldissouky A, El-Asasery MA, Elsayed DS, Alaswad EA. Synthesis, characterization, computational and dyeing behavior of Cu(II) and Zn(II) metal complexes derived from azo-Schiff bases containing phenol derivatives. *BMC Chem.*, 2025; 19(1): 207.
35. Waziri I, Wahab OO, Mala GA, Ismaila MB, Umaru U, Abd El-Maksoud MS, Wakil IM, Yusuf TL. Synthesis, characterization, biological evaluation, DFT calculations, and molecular docking study of transition metal complexes derived from a Schiff base ligand. *Chem. Biodivers.*, 2025; 22(11): 00940.
36. Sakhare KB, Sarwade KN, Joshi HU, Sakhare MA. Green route for efficient synthesis of metal complexes of 4-bromo-2-((E)-((2-hydroxyphenyl)imino)methyl)-6-((E)-(3-nitrophenyl)diazenyl)phenol and its anti-hyperglycemia, anticancer and antimicrobial assessment. *J Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2025; 00: 64-64.
37. Mohammed ZH, Jawad SA. Preparation, diagnosis and study of the effect of the biological activity of multi dentate azo-Schiff ligand and Cu(II), Zn(II) complexes. *J Kufa Chem. Sci.*, 2025; 4(2): 615-630.
38. Hassan JF, Hassan SS. Preparation, characterization, and studying the biological activity of Schiff base metal complexes derived from cephalexin with 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde. *Baghdad Sci. J.*, 2025; 22(10): 3299-3309.
39. El-Sonbati AZ, El-Bindary AA, Mansour NM, El-Zahed MM. Novel bivalent transition metal complexes based on a 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine Schiff base ligand: synthesis elucidation, antimicrobial evaluation, antioxidant and molecular docking studies. *BMC Chem.*, 2025; 19(1): 177.
40. Oladipo S, Adeleke AA, Badeji AA, Babalola KI, Labulo AH, Hassan I, Yussuf ST, Olalekan SO. Computational investigation and biological activity of selected Schiff bases. *J Niger Soc. Phys. Sci.*, 2024; 2103-2103.

41. Ali DN, Hussein KA, Faeq M, Imran Y, Ahmed WA. Molecular docking, synthesis of new Schiff base derivatives, and study of their biological activity. *Al-Nahrain J Sci.*, 2024; 27(5): 25-34.
42. Prabhakar UPS, Periyasami G, Karthikeyan P. Nanostructured metal oxides synthesized via simple thermal decomposition of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) Schiff base complexes: characterization and antimicrobial activity. *Inorg. Chem. Commun*, 2024; 159: 111796.
43. Vaikosen EN, Bunu SJ, Miediegha O, Chilaka UP, Echendu CE, Usifoh CO. Synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of some Schiff base derivatives. *Pharm. Drug. Dev.*, 2024; 3: 1-8.
44. Arulmozhi S, Sasikumar G, Subramani A, Mohammed MKA, Askar Ali SJ, Ponnusamy S, Jabir MS, Elgorban AM, Zhang W, Natarajan H. Chemical, pharmacological, and theoretical aspects of some transition metal(II) complexes derived from pyrrole azine Schiff base. *ACS Omega.*, 2023; 8(38): 34458-34470.
45. Olanrewaju AA, Oke DG, Adekunle DO, Adeleke OA, Akinola OT, Emmanuel AV, Oyenyin OE. Synthesis, in-vitro and in-silico antibacterial and computational studies of selected thiosemicarbazone-benzaldehyde derivatives as potential antibiotics. *SN Appl. Sci.*, 2023; 5(8): 213.
46. Al-Fakeh MS, Alsikhan MA, Alnawmasi JS. Physico-chemical study of Mn(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Cr(III), and Pd(II) complexes with Schiff-base and aminopyrimidyl derivatives and anti-cancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial applications. *Molecules*, 2023; 28(6): 2555.
47. Awolope RO, Ejidike IP, Clayton HS. Schiff base metal complexes as dual antioxidant and antimicrobial agents. *J Appl. Pharm. Sci.*, 2023; 13(3): 132-140.
48. Hussaini SY, Abdulkadir M, Panda NA, Fagge II, Danjaji HI, Sani S. Synthesis, analysis and antibacterial studies of Co(II) and Ni(II) Schiff base complexes derived from 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and benzaldehyde. *Sch Int. J Chem. Mater. Sci.*, 2023; 6(3): 47-52.
49. Aminu IK, Daura AA. Synthesis, characterization and study of antimicrobial activity of Mn(II) and Ni(II) complexes with Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 1-naphthylamine. *Am J Appl. Chem.*, 2023; 11(3): 86-94.
50. Ahmed SA, Saeed IA, Salih SM. Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, and antimicrobial studies of new Schiff bases and their metal complexes. *Egypt. J Chem.*, 2023; 66(4): 325-333.

51. Hassan AM, Said AO, Heakal BH, Younis A, Aboulthana WM, Mady MF. Green synthesis, characterization, antimicrobial and anticancer screening of new metal complexes incorporating Schiff base. *ACS Omega*, 2022; 7(36): 32418-32431.
52. Buldurun K, Turan N, Savci A, Alan Y, Colak N. Synthesis, characterization, X-ray diffraction analysis of a tridentate Schiff base ligand and its complexes with Co(II), Fe(II), Pd(II) and Ru(II): bioactivity studies. *Iran. J Chem. Chem. Eng.*, 2022; 41(8): 2635-2649.
53. Sani S, Siraj IT, Kurawa MA, Abdul Halim SN. An efficient synthetic route, characterization and antimicrobial evaluation of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Schiff base complexes. *Bull Chem. Soc. Ethiop*, 2022; 36(4): 801-813.
54. Rangaswamy V, Renuka S, Venda I. Synthesis, spectral characterization and antibacterial activity of transition metal(II) complexes of tetradentate Schiff base ligand. *Mater Today Proc.*, 2022; 51: 1810-1816.
55. Yahaya NP, Mukhtar MS. Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of mixed ligands of Schiff base and its metal(II) complexes derived from ampicillin, 3-aminophenol and benzaldehyde. *Science*, 2021; 9(1): 9-13.
56. Nibila TA, Soufeena PP, Periyat P, Aravindakshan KK. Synthesis, structural characterization and biological activities of transition metal complexes derived from 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde N(4)-methyl(phenyl)thiosemicarbazone. *J Mol. Struct.*, 2021; 1231: 129938.
57. Borase JN, Mahale RG, Rajput SS, Shirsath DS. Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of heterocyclic methyl substituted pyridine Schiff base transition metal complexes. *SN Appl. Sci.*, 2021; 3(2): 197.
58. El-Gamasy SM, Ebrahim S. 4N donor atoms moiety of transition metal complexes of a Schiff base ligand: synthesis, characterization and biological activities study. *Egypt. J Chem.*, 2021; 64(10): 5975-5987.
59. Abdulsayid FA, Hasan HM, Bouagila RA. Synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial studies of Schiff base and its metal complexes. *Int. Res. J Pure. Appl. Chem.*, 2020; 21(17): 1-9.
60. Usman B, Udofia L, Sahura A, Fa'iza I. Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity evaluation of metal(II) complexes derived from (E)-N-benzylidene acetamide Schiff base. *Int. J Sci. Res. Eng. Dev.*, 2020; 3(3): 1181-1186.
61. Abd El-Razek SE, El-Gamasy SM, Hassan M, Abdel-Aziz MS, Nasr SM. Transition metal complexes of a multidentate Schiff base ligand containing guanidine moiety:

- synthesis, characterization, anti-cancer effect, and anti-microbial activity. *J Mol. Struct.*, 2020; 1203: 127381.
62. Sumrra SH, Sahrish I, Raza MA, Ahmad Z, Zafar MN, Chohan ZH, Khalid M, Ahmed S. Efficient synthesis, characterization, and in vitro bactericidal studies of unsymmetrically substituted triazole-derived Schiff base ligand and its transition metal complexes. *Monatsh Chem.*, 2020; 151(4): 549-557.
63. Otuokere IE, Anyanwu JC, Igwe KK. Ni(II) complex of a novel Schiff base derived from benzaldehyde and sulphathiazole: synthesis, characterization and antibacterial studies. *Commun. Phys. Sci.*, 2020; 5(2): 145-155.
64. Pervaiz M, Ahmad I, Yousaf M, Kirn S, Munawar A, Saeed Z, Adnan A, et al. Synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial studies of amino acid derivative Schiff base metal (Co, Mn, Cu, and Cd) complexes. *Spectrochim Acta. A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc*, 2019; 206: 642-649.
65. Vinusha HM, Kollur SP, Revanasiddappa HD, Ramu R, Shirahatti PS, Nagendra Prasad MN, Chandrashekar S, Begum M. Preparation, spectral characterization and biological applications of Schiff base ligand and its transition metal complexes. *Results. Chem.*, 2019; 1: 100012.
66. Eugene-Osoikhia TT, Akinpelu IO, Odiaka TI. Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of transition metal complexes of Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and L-tyrosine amino acid. *Niger J Chem. Res.*, 2019; 24(1): 46-56.
67. Hossain MS, Zakaria CM, Zahan MK. Synthesis and characterization with antimicrobial activity studies on some transition metal complexes of N,O donor novel Schiff base ligand. *J Sci. Res.*, 2017; 9(2): 209-218.
68. Mahalaksmi N, Kuppusamy M, Sureshkumar R, Vanitha C. Synthesis, spectroscopic studies and antibacterial activity of novel Schiff base metal complexes. *Int. Res. J Eng. Technol.*, 2017; 4(10): 1519-1527.